

CLINICAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL FACTORS FOR BACTERIA IN BLOOD AND BILE AMONG PATIENTS WITH ACUTE CHOLANGITIS*Fuss J.,**PhD, St.Paraskeva medical center**Voloboyeva A.,**Communal Municipal Clinical Hospital 8, Lviv**Polovyj V.**Doctor of medical science,**Bukovinian State Medical University, Chernovtsy***Abstract**

Background. Acute cholangitis is a clinical syndrome caused by bacterial infection in the biliary system.

Methods. Patients with acute cholangitis admitted to hospital between January 2018 and December 2023. The diagnostic criteria for acute cholangitis were based on Tokyo Guidelines 18.

Results. A total of 250 patients had bacterial growth in bile. Alanine aminotransferase concentration and duration of antibiotic use correlated with bacteria in bile.

Conclusion. The commonly isolated bacteria from bile samples in patients with acute cholangitis were *E.coli*, *Kl.pneumoniae*, and *E.faecalis*. Age, C-reactive protein, duration of antibiotic usage, alanine aminotransferase level were independent risk factors, and the predictive model could efficiently identify the patients with a high risk of bacteria in bile when invasive operations are conducted.

Keywords: acute cholangitis, bacteria, blood culture, bile culture.

Introduction. Acute cholangitis, the most common hepatobiliary system disease, is an infectious condition caused by partial or complete obstruction of the biliary system and can have life-threatening consequences if not given timely treatment [1,2]. Fever, abdominal pain, and jaundice are typical clinical manifestations of patients with acute cholangitis and obstruction of the bile duct is the main cause biliary obstruction [3].

Controlling biliary infections and obstruction release are the most common two important strategies in the clinical management of acute cholangitis. Treatment methods include intravenous fluid, antibiotics administration, and biliary drainage [4,5]. The presents of bacteria in bile increased the risk of entering the circulation system when invasive operations were conducted to remove the stone in the biliary duct system, consequently resulting in systemic infections [6]. However, there is limited data on risk factors related to positive culture results in bile specimens before bile drainage. Therefore, bile samples were collected to analyze the distribution of bacteria that remains in patients with acute cholangitis after antibiotic treatment. Clinical manifestations and laboratory tests upon admission were reviewed to predict the presence of bacteria in bile when bile drainage was conducted [7,8].

Material and methods. This was a retrospective study. Patients with acute cholangitis admitted to a

St.Paraskeva medical center, Communal Clinical hospital 8, department of surgery Pustomyty Hospital between January 2018 and December 2023. The diagnostic criteria for acute cholangitis were based on Tokyo Guidelines 18. Data were collected retrospectively by local investigators using electronic case report forms (eCRF) then centralized and anonymized. The following data were collected: age, gender, cardiovascular diseases (coronary artery diseases or chronic heart failure), hypertension, other comorbidities (e.g. diabetes mellitus, cancer, immune deficiency, cirrhosis, chronic renal failure), clinical symptoms (abdominal pain, jaundice, diarrhea, chills) at ICU admission. Laboratory examinations of blood cell components and other analyses were collected within 24h during hospitalization.

Results. According to the bile culture results, 322 patients with acute cholangitis were divided into the following group: bacteria in bile – group I (212) and control (110) groups – group II.

The median age was 66 years with a twofold higher incidence of men (65%). Patient characteristics are summarized in Table 1. Commodities were frequent, notably diabetes (n = 96, 45%), cardiovascular diseases (n = 156, 73%) and active solid tumors (n = 45, 21%). Abdominal pain (93%) and jaundice (85%), which are classical clinical signs of AC, were frequently observed but fever (defined by a temperature > 38 °C) was only reported in 135 patients (64%).

Table 1

General characteristics of patients			
Characteristics		Group I (n=212)	Group II (n=110)
Gender			
	Male	146	68
	Female	66	42
Age (years)		72 (60-84)	66 (46-74)
Commodities	Diabetes	96 (45%)	58 (53%)
	Hypertension	112 (53%)	64 (58%)
	Cardiovascular disease	156 (73%)	98 (89%)
	Chronic kidney disease	30 (14%)	20 (18%)
	Cirrhosis	20 (9,5%)	8 (7%)
	Cancer and hematologic malignancies	45 (21%)	23 (21%)
Biliary drainage procedure	Percutaneous derivation	22 (10%)	18 (16%)
	ERCP	198 (93%)	92 (84%)
	Surgery	12 (5,7%)	8 (7%)
Complications after ERCP	Bleeding	35 (16,5%)	22 (20%)
	Gastrointestinal perforation	27 (13%)	15 (14%)
	Pancreatitis	31 (15%)	17 (15,5%)

At ICU admission, patients with AC had severe disease, with sepsis (), septic shock () and a high SOFA score (). A high proportion of patients had renal (□) failure, coagulopathy and lactic acidosis. Finally, in ICU

mortality reached 18%, half of the death occurring within the first 10 days of ICU admission (table 2).

Table 2

Clinical and biological parameters of patients with acute cholangitis				
Characteristic		Group I (n=212)	Group II (n=110)	p-value
Clinical signs	Abdominal pain	198 (93%)	89 (81%)	
	jaundice	180 (85%)	78 (71%)	
	chills	124 (59%)	64 (58%)	
	Temperature >38	135 (64%)	85 (77%)	
Biological parameters	Leukocytes (*10 ⁹ /L)	0,84 (0,42-1,34)	1,07 (0,7-1,5)	<0,001
	Platelets (*10 ⁹ /L)	10,00 (9,0-10,8)	10,00 (9,0-10,8)	0,942
	Alanine aminotransferaze (U/l)	107,00 (45,00-220,00)	190,00 (80,00-350,00)	<0,001
	Aspartate aminotransferase (U/l)	95,00 (40,00-250,00)	150,00 (50,00-300,00)	0,001
	Total blood bilirubin (μM)	44,00 (18,50-80,50)	45,50 (22,00-80,50)	0,406
	Serum creatinine (μM)	65,00 (54,00-84,00)	61,00 (50,00-76,00)	0,018
	C-reactive protein (mg/l)	25,00 (5,00-70,00)	8,5 (2,50-44,50)	<0,001

Positive blood culture was frequently reported in patients with AC (n=240/322). Bile culture was only performed in 145/322 and was positive in 75% of the cases (250). microbiological data are summarized in Table 3. in blood or bile culture, the most frequently identified bacteria were gram-negative bacilli (82%)

and gram positive (17%). The most frequently identified bacteria were Escherichia coli (47%), Kl.pneumonia (11%), Enterococcus faecalis (7%), Enterobacter cloacae (6,5%) and Pseudomonas aeruginosa (4,5%). finally, an infection caused by Extended spectrum beta lactamase (ESBL) – producing bacteria was observed in 35 AC patients.

Microbiological data in blood and bile culture

Germes	Blood	Bile
Positive culture	240 (75%)	145 (45%)
Total pathogens	318 (98%)	250 (78%)
Gram negative bacilli	264 (82%)	196 (61%)
Escherichia coli	152 (47%)	82 (25%)
Kl.pneumonia	35 (11%)	20 (6%)
Enterobacter cloacae	21 (6,5%)	16 (5%)
Kl. oxytoca	15 (4,5%)	8 (2,5%)
Ps.aeruginosa	15 (4,5%)	18 (5,6%)
ESBL	35 (11%)	30 (9,3%)
Gram positive bacilli	54 (17%)	54 (17%)
Enterococcus faecium	23 (7%)	25 (7,8%)
Streptococcus spp.	19 (6%)	6 (1,9%)
Enterococcus faecalis	16 (5%)	38 (12%)
Staphylococcus aureus	4 (1,3%)	6 (1,9%)
Other GP	13 (4%)	11 (3,5%)

Discussion. Infection of biliary system causes acute cholangitis, a clinical condition that may result in death if not treated appropriately. Biliary obstruction, followed by bacteria ascending into the bile duct, is an important factor in the pathogenesis of acute cholangitis [9,10]. However, bacteria can remain in the bile despite antibiotic usage. In the study, the distribution of bacteria in the bile was determined, and multiple indicators of the first laboratory examination during hospitalization were analyzed to determine the risk factors for bacteria in the bile for patients with cholangitis [11].

It was found that age was independent risk factor for bacterial bile in patients with acute cholangitis, which might be attributed to a decline in defense response immunity with aging, and the body's weakened resistance to pathogens [12]. Furthermore, the incidence of acute cholangitis is higher in older people than in younger people. As a diagnostic indicator of acute cholangitis, elevated C-protein level suggest bacterial infection. However, the results of this study demonstrated that only a substantially elevated level could be indicative of the presence of bacteria in bile specimens based on the limited contribution [13].

Conclusion. The commonly isolated bacteria from bile samples in patients with acute cholangitis were *E.coli*, *Kl.pneumoniae*, and *E.faecalis*. Age, C-reactive protein, duration of antibiotic usage, alanine aminotransferase level were independent risk factors, and the predictive model could efficiently identify the patients with a high risk of bacteria in bile when invasive operations are conducted.

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